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ABSTRACTS

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SaniSafe - Technological Solutions for Safe Disposal of Menstrual Waste

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Abstract: The proposed solution SaniSafe heralds a groundbreaking innovation aimed at the responsible disposal of diverse menstrual waste, including pads, tampons, and cups, signifying a pivotal stride in women's health and environmental sustainability. Its distinctive system efficiently manages various menstrual waste types by commencing with meticulous segregation to tailor subsequent treatment processes. The introduction of ultraviolet (UV) treatment ensures the sterilization of items, guaranteeing pathogen elimination and enhancing overall safety. Subsequent hydrogen peroxide-based treatment removes menstrual blood from pads while melting and remolding cups, and breaking down pads and tampons into constituent materials. This innovative treatment isolates cellulose from pads and tampons, presenting reusable materials to address environmental concerns. Derived cellulose and plastic materials post-treatment hold vast potential across industries, offering sustainable alternatives to traditional resources. Beyond technical advancements, this prototype challenges societal taboos related to menstrual waste disposal, aiming to transform perceptions and practices, and fostering an inclusive environment. Not only does it control menstrual waste, but it also advances a comprehensive understanding of women's health and hygiene. This pioneering prototype stands as a catalyst for global change, offering a method that enhances living standards worldwide. Its innovative approach transforms disposal processes, carrying immense commercial potential. In essence, this technological breakthrough signifies a milestone in menstrual waste management, employing unique collection, segregation, and treatment methods alongside material reutilization possibilities. It marks a step towards an inclusive, sustainable, and hygienic future, bridging critical gaps in waste management and societal attitudes.

Keywords: Menstrual waste management, sustainable disposal solution, environmental innovation, women's health.

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